

PRINCIPLES OF ACCOUNTING – QUICK CASES

Unit 8: The Double-Entry Trilogy

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CASE OUTLINE

The Double-Entry Trilogy is a set of three interactive learning games that support the development of core skills in financial accounting. The games focus on double-entry bookkeeping, journal entries, and balance sheet preparation, based on IFRS accounting practices.

The trilogy includes three games:

1. Transaction Match

Learners review business transactions and match each one to the correct debit and credit accounts. This activity applies the dual aspect principle and supports recognition of account types.

2. Balance Builder

Learners allocate account balances to the appropriate section of the balance sheet: assets, liabilities, or equity. The activity links transactions to their effect on financial position.

3. Journal Journey

Learners complete journal entries using formal structure and apply UK accounting rules. This game involves selecting accounts, applying debit and credit logic, and recording full double-entry entries.

Each game includes repeated practice, real-time feedback, and increasing complexity. The games are suitable for classroom use or independent study, and support both formative and summative assessment. They allow repeated engagement, immediate correction, and active involvement in accounting processes.

CASE RESOURCES

- Game platform: <https://drmichaelguo.github.io/game-double-entry/>
- Screenshots of the interface are provided below.

Accounting Games

Develop your accounting skills through interactive gameplay

Transaction Match

Match debit and credit entries for accounting transactions to build your understanding of the double entry system.

Play

Balance Builder

Create balanced financial statements by categorising accounts and analyse the impact on your balance sheet.

Play

Journal Journey

Record business transactions in proper journal entry format following UK accounting standards and practices.

Play

Transaction Match

Match the correct debit and credit entries for each transaction

How to Play

1. Read the transaction description
2. Drag the correct accounts to the debit and credit columns
3. Check your answer and move to the next transaction
4. Complete all transactions to win!

Select Difficulty

Easy Medium Hard

Score: 0 Time: 00:00

Transaction:
Purchased office equipment for £5,000 in cash.

Debit	Credit
Drag account here	Drag account here

Check Answer Next Transaction Reset

Balance Builder

Create balanced financial statements from account information

How to Play

1. Review the account balances provided
2. Drag each account to the correct section of the financial statement
3. Ensure your statement balances correctly
4. Submit your solution when ready

Select Difficulty

Easy Medium Hard

Score: 0 Time: 00:10

Company Information:
XYZ Corporation is finalising its year-end financial statements for 2025.

Account Balances

Ordinary Shares: £15,000	Trade Payables: £12,000
Loans Payable: £25,000	Cash: £22,000
Retained Profits: £15,000	Investments: £15,000
Office Equipment: £30,000	

[Balance Sheet](#)

Journal Journey

Record transactions in proper journal entry format

How to Play

1. Read the transaction description
2. Select accounts from the dropdown menus
3. Enter the correct amounts for each account
4. Choose whether each account is debited or credited
5. Check your answer and continue to the next transaction

Select Difficulty

Easy Medium Hard

Score: 0 Time: 00:00

Transaction:
Purchased equipment for £10,000, paying £4,000 in cash and financing the remainder with a loan payable.

Journal Entry

Account	Debit	Credit
Add Account Row		
Total Debits:		£0
Total Credits:		£0

Not Balanced

[Check Answer](#) [Next Transaction](#) [Reset](#)

CASE QUESTIONS AND DISCUSSION

1. In the *Transaction Match* game, which transactions were most difficult to classify? Why?
2. How did *Balance Builder* improve your understanding of the accounting equation?
3. In *Journal Journey*, what types of errors occurred when you completed journal entries?
4. How did interactive feedback influence your understanding compared to static textbook questions?
5. Based on your performance in the games, which topics in double-entry recording require further review?